

Research

A structural model for analyzing supply chain risks from the standpoint of the Chinese and Bangladeshi apparel industries

Janiefer Jabbar Jesha^{1*}, Ma Jiaqi^{2*}, Jourge Shovon Biswas³, Mahmuda Akter⁴

¹Postgraduate Student, College of Economics Management, Business Administration, Taiyuan University of Technology

²Professor, College of Economics Management, Business Administration, Taiyuan University of Technology

³Postgraduate Student, College of Economics Management, Business Administration, Taiyuan University of Technology

⁴Postgraduate Student, Department of Education Management, School of Economics and Management, Huzhou University

Abstract: A structural model for analyzing supply chain risks from the perspectives of China and Bangladesh Supply chain networks are becoming more and more vulnerable to ambiguities and challenges in the current business environment. The global reach of the supply chain networks in China and Bangladesh for the ready-to-wear (RMG) business leaves it vulnerable to escalating risks and disruptions. This study aids in the creation of fresh methods for risk assessment in order to pinpoint implementation difficulties in the apparel and textile supply chain between China and Bangladesh. Focus on how risk assessment can be used in these two nations to control social risks at the supplier level. A hierarchical structural model was developed using an interpretive structural modeling (ISM) method to achieve this. Additionally, MICMAC (Matriced' Impacts Cruoses Multiplication Applique an un Classement) analysis was utilized to classify the dangers according to driving and dependency power. The results showed that disruption risk was the most important risk in the RMG market. The results of this study will help industrial managers take the necessary remedial action to lower supply chain risks in the apparel industry.

Keywords: Supply chain, SCRM, ISM, Readymade Garments factory

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 13 December, 2022; **Published:** 22 December, 2022

How to cite this article: Author (2022). A structural model for analyzing supply chain risks from the standpoint of the Chinese and Bangladeshi apparel industries. *North American Academic Research*, 5(12), 57-63. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7469917>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2022 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

In Bangladesh, the first Chinese companies entered in 1997; today, there are about 400 of them. China has supported the growing apparel market, which is anticipated to exceed \$50 billion in sales by 2021. Bangladesh, which has the lowest wages in the region, has looked for a range of international partners to help it avoid becoming caught in China's "debt trap."

According to the local Bangladesh newspaper The Financial Express, China has become a major market for Bangladeshi textile output for the past three seasons. Faced with growing wages, China is gradually relinquishing its role as the "world's factory," eventually transforming into a massive global consumer thanks to a surge in domestic demand. According to Lin Yun Feng of FashionMag.com, the adjustment has caused China to withdraw from certain types of entry-level manufacture in order to better management of its premium categories.

The head of the Chinese delegation and vice president of the CCPIT attends the Texworld trade show in Paris on a regular basis, with whom the Chinese Chamber partnered to build the Apparel Sourcing satellite event. Lin Feng Yun had mentioned Bangladesh as a potential market for the Chinese textile industry.

The garment industry is renowned for its ferocious competition and high profit margins (Pentecost and Andrews, 2010). Supply networks have grown more intricate as a result of the industry's heightened competition (Perry and Towers, 2009). The hazards in the RMG supply chain have increased as a result of this complexity. The risks in Bangladesh's RMG supply chain were evaluated using interpretive structural modeling (ISM). ISM explores connections and places components in order of how dominant they are over one another. 17 risks were first found in a literature review. Based on professional judgment, the top ten hazards were selected, and contextual links were created for further research. Following ISM, MICMAC analysis was used to classify the hazards based on driving and reliance on electricity. The following queries about this study seem intriguing:

Q1. What are the major risks involved in in managing supply chains between China and Bangladesh?

Q2. From the standpoint of the Bangladesh and China RMG industry, what is the hierarchical connection among the highlighted risks?

Q3. What is Supplier Management risk reduction techniques to allay worries about all offshore risk in China's and Bangladesh's supply chains?

Q4. What should be to do mitigate the risks in this situation?

The following summarizes the paper: 1The pertinent literature is discussed. describes the study's methodology. 2The development of the study's framework. 3Presents the arguments and conclusions. 4Contains the recommendations for further research, managerial implications, and conclusions.

Literature Review

This section summarizes the background of global SCM practices, possible risks, risk mitigation strategies, and the methodology for evaluating global SCM risks.

- **Background of Global SCM**

The goal of global supply chain management is to optimize cost-effectiveness and customer service by planning how the whole supply chain will function as one unit. Other goals include enhancing the delivery time of your goods and your flexibility in handling consumer contacts. It consists of management procedures that connect the network of distributors, producers, warehouses, and retail establishments to ensure that the right goods are sourced, supplied, produced, and shipped in the right quantities, to the right locations, at the right times, and are received in good condition. Resources, materials, and information flows must be properly linked to ensure timely delivery of purchase orders, shipping notifications, waybills, and invoicing (including raw and finished products).

- SCRM approaches that have been studied in a comparable way many academics have defined SCRM as the collaboration of supply chain parties in order to reduce risk and maintain reliability. By identifying risks and the drivers that produce them.

Table 1 shows the major supply chain hazards found between China and Bangladesh based on the associated research.

Law and politics of export restriction	The causes of export limitations are still a mystery to us. To my knowledge, no research looked at the many political and economic factors that influence export limits in the apparel industry.
Delays	Unfortunately, high lead times might cause even more delays in shipments. There are numerous potential for things to go wrong in the global supply chain since there are so many processes and such enormous distances for commodities to go.
Cash flow	Cash flow management is a major concern in every company, but it's more difficult in global logistics and supply chain management.
Licensing procedure	The Commerce Department's Proposed Supply Chain Regulations and Licensing Procedure continue to be criticized by business groups.
Export Tax	The export tax transfers wealth from producers to consumers and the government. The magnitudes of $(A+C)$, A , $(E+F+G+H)$, and the political weights the government allocates to producers, consumers, and tax revenue determine whether a welfare-maximizing government implements export limitation.
International trade and Economic law	Macroeconomics factors, such as GDP in Garments, and the number of regional trade agreement (RTA) partners.
Demand	When net exporter does not levy an export tax in response to an increase in import demand, the domestic price rises.
Covid 19	Several major grain exporting routes between China and Bangladesh were disrupted by the COVID-19 outbreak.
Global trade alert	Another issue is that, because to missing factors and reverse causation, market power and RTA partners might be endogenous. For instance, if unobserved time-varying variables influence country's market power/RTA formation at the same time.
Data management	The chance to manage supply and demand is cited by 36% of respondents as a significant reason for their analytics endeavor. Machine learning is being considered by 19 percent of businesses to increase prediction accuracy.
Exchange rate	When spending a vacation overseas, exchange rate changes are unimportant. When managing a worldwide supply chain, however, even little changes in foreign currency rates can drastically boost expenses.
Exposure to Risk	Bangladesh and China, which have very low labor and manufacturing costs, are also known for having unstable governments and currencies. Changes in leadership and policy at a local level can have a big impact on the global supply chain.
Quality control and defeat	Quality concerns might sometimes be difficult to deal with. Businesses must, for example, evaluate the variances in acceptable defect levels among these two nations. It's critical to establish the intended quality level and the proportion of acceptable faults in advance. It's also a good idea to specify who is liable and what will happen if there is a future disagreement.
Language Barriers	Another disadvantage to consider is that day-to-day activities will be conducted in a different language between these two countries.

The proposed methodology's foundation

This research has utilized a variety of methodology to identify the most important hazards to SCM and potential mitigation strategies in between China and Bangladesh. Table 2 summarizes the results of some of these SCRM research.

Table 2 Summary of studies on supply chain risks and concerned methodologies.

Sources	Objectives and Methodology Used
Qazi et al. (2018)	Develop a supply chain risk network management approach to assess the degree of dependency among risks, as well as many performance measurement criteria and mitigation strategies.
Jahre (2017)	To have a better understanding of humanitarian supply chain risk reduction measures.
Giannakis and Papadopoulos (2016)	To design a risk management methodology for supply chain sustainability from an operational standpoint. Analysis of the mode and consequences of failure.
Zhao et al. (2013)	To learn more about the impact of risks on supply chain performance. Modeling of structural equations (SEM).
Wieland and Marcus Wallenburg, 2012	The purpose of this study is to see how SCRM affects supply chain performance. Modeling of structural equations.
Kleindorfer and Saad (2005)	Framework for reducing supply chain risk is suggested. thorough literature review.
Kleindorfer and Saad (2005)	Research opportunities online in SCRM. comprehensive literature review

Using the suggested framework in practice

Two firms in the clothing industry from China and Bangladesh were chosen to test the viability of the suggested framework. The RMG sector in Bangladesh is well-versed in these businesses. Due to the multiple risks involved in this process, both parties, however, are having trouble properly integrating SCM methods into the company. Therefore, specialists from several departments of these companies served as the respondents to this study. These respondents included operational process managers from the purchase and supply division, supply production leaders, and production executives. The methods used to create the ISM were continually assessed by the specialists. Opinions were gathered and monitored independently in order to prevent bias.

ISM analysis

The ISM process's steps are thoroughly explained here. Phase 1: Determining the risk factors in the supply chain. The primary risk factors discovered after a review of related literature are shown in Table 2. In the RMG business, a list of 10 significant supply chain risks was produced using the opinions of specialists.

The relationship between two related components *i* and *j* was shown using the following four symbols to indicate its direction:

- a) V: Factor *i* affects factor *j*
- b) A: Factor *i* is affected by factor *j*
- c) X: Factors *i* and *j* affect each other
- d) O: Factors *i* and *j* are unrelated

This phase of the ISM approach was associated with reachability matrix of the system variables. For this, the four symbols (i.e., V, A, X or O) of the SSIM were replaced with a 1 or 0 to convert the SSIM into a reachability matrix.

Table 3 Variables Risk for ISM

Risk	Risk variation notation
Demand	R1
Delay	R2
Suppliers Performance	R3
Disruption	R4
Supply network design	R5
Exchange Rate and transactions cost	R6
Quality control and defects	R7
Supply network design	R8
Export tax	R9
Language berries	R10

To reach a consensus, SSIM and the experts were debated at the same time. The SSIM matrix was completed based on consensus among experts.

Risk j Risk i

R1 R2 R3 R4 R5 R6 R7 R8 R9 R10

The binary relationships are displayed. The reachability matrix was created by following the laws of substitution. This phase involved examining the reachability matrix's transitivity. The transitivity matrix for the supply chain risks is based on the guidelines given in i. The essential procedures were carried out in order to determine the ISM levels after calculating the transitivity matrix. The ISM's level partitioning procedure involved the intricate iterations. A conical matrix of SCM dangers was constructed based on the levels found in the previous stage. Transitivity was taken into consideration while calculating the risks' driving and relying capabilities.

Diagraph

R1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
R2	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
R3	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
R4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
R5	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
R6	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
R7	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
R8	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
R9	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1

R10	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
-----	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

The supply chain hazards of the Bangladesh RMG industry were included in a digraph that was created using the idea of representing relationships as nodes and edges. By substituting statements for the factor nodes in the digraph, an ISM was created. The dependent variables identified were demand (R1), delay/lead time (R2), supplier performance (R3), and (R5). Supply chain network design Supply network design (R5) exhibited the strongest dependence out of all of these factors. All other hazards indicated in this study also influenced it. The linking factors in the next quadrant (quadrant C), which were distinguished by strong driving force and dependence, were displayed. There were no variables in this section.

Finally, independent variables with more driving force and less reliance were present in the last quarter (quadrant D). The independent factors were found as disruption (R4), Exchange Rate and transactions cost (R6), Export tax (R9), and disruption (R4). The disruption risk (R4) was the one with the most driving strength, meaning it was the one that drove all other risks. The management of the RMG sector in Bangladesh and China should be well aware of these dangers.

Risk mitigation Strategies

Informants were questioned about these two countries supply chain risk mitigation methods to complement the interviews' discussion of offshore concerns. Across all interviews, trends and patterns were found. In order to group the similar activities done by each fashion brand, four risk mitigation techniques were thus presented. The following strategies were listed: Global Health, **Supplier Management, Factory Diversification, International Trade Implications, and Economic Crisis.**

Conclusion Research Limitation and Future Research

Given that this study focused mostly on qualitative data, there are several limitations to be aware of and potential areas for further research. Four supply chain experts from four different firms were interviewed, and these interviews served as the primary source of information for data gathering. Using the similarities between the interviews as a starting point, interpretations and insights were generated. The theories that emerged from the interviews, the literature study was employed. But there is a chance to improve theory and check the accuracy of the recent discoveries through more empirical research.

Although the four organizations that were analyzed are varied and have unique traits, more businesses should be assessed. It is probable that the organization's size also influenced their choice. Future scholars may create more comprehensive theories through further interviews or a quantitative study. A framework for creating measures for the subsequent research phases might be developed using the literature review and interview data from this study.

The supply chain management decision-making process is the main topic of this study. Given that risk management was the primary driver of the production change, further challenges are expected to appear. Crisis management would probably be approached on a case-by-case basis because each obstacle is distinct. Concerns about a rise in taxes on items from Bangladesh and China were present at the time the interviews were conducted. As a result, this influenced the choice. Another risk surfaced at the conclusion of the interviews. The COVID-19 outbreak on supply chains and the supply chain. It would be important to continue this research and see how apparel manufacturers are reducing pandemic risk. There are important topics that require more research.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Qazi, A., Dickson, A., Quigley, J., Gaudenzi, B., 2018. Supply chain risk network management: a Bayesian belief network and expected utility based approach for managing supply chain risks. *Int. J. Prod. Econ.* 196, 24–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2017.11.008>.
- [1] Qi, L., Lee, K., 2015. Supply chain risk mitigations with expedited shipping. *Omega*.
- [2] Raj, T., Attri, R., 2010. Quantifying barriers to implementing total quality management (TQM). *Eur. J. Ind. Eng.* 4 (3), 308–335. <https://doi.org/10.1504/EJIE.2010.033333>.
- [3] Rajesh, R., Ravi, V., 2015. Modeling enablers of supply chain risk mitigation in electronic supply chains: a Grey-DEMATEL approach. *Compute. Ind. Eng.* 87, 126–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2015.04.028>.
- [4] supply chain management: decision making under bounded rationality. *Int. J. Oper. Prod. Manage.* 34 (5), 695–719. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOPM-10-2012-0449>.
- [5] Rueda, X., Garrett, R.D., Lambin, E.F., 2017. Corporate investments in supply chain sustainability: selecting instruments in the agri-food industry. *J. Clean. Prod.* 142, 2480–2492. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.11.026>.
- [6] Tang, C.S., 2006a. Perspectives in supply chain risk management: a review. *Ssrn* 103, 451–488. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.925274>.
- [7] Shibin, K.T., Gunasekaran, A., Dubey, R., 2017. Explaining sustainable supply chain performance using a total interpretive structural modeling approach. *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 12, 104–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2017.06.003>.
- [8] Snyder, L.V., Atan, Z., Peng, P., Rong, Y., Schmitt, A.J., Sinoysal, B., 2016. OR/MS models for supply chain disruptions: a review. *IIE Trans.* 48 (2), 89–109.
- [9] Sodhi, M.S., Son, B., Tang, C.S., 2012. Researchers' perspectives on supply chain risk management. *Prod. Oper. Manag.* 21 (1), 1–13.
- [10] Enablers and barriers of flexible green supply chain management: a total interpretive structural modeling approach. *Glob. J. Flex. Syst. Manag.* 17 (2), 171–188.
- [11] Robust strategies for mitigating supply chain disruptions. *Int. J. Logist. Res. Appl.* 9 (1), 33–45.
- [12] Tang, C., Tomlin, B., 2008. The power of flexibility for mitigating supply chain risks. *Int. J. Prod. Econ.* 116 (1), 12–27.

